

Light Upconversion by Triplet-Triplet Annihilation in Diphenylanthracene-Based Copolymers

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Low-power light upconversion by triplet-triplet annihilation (TTA-UC) was only recently achieved in glassy materials. Here, a new strategy based on covalent tethering of diphenylanthracene (DPA) emitters to a polymeric backbone is reported. The design aims to optimize the efficiency of this photophysical process in glassy polymeric materials by increasing the emitter content. To that end, DPA molecules were covalently attached to a methacrylate-type monomer and further copolymerized with methylmethacrylate (MMA). Green-to-blue (543 to 440 nm) upconversion was observed at power densities as low as 32 mW/cm² in films prepared by solution casting and compression molding (co)polymers containing 8-72 wt% of DPA and palladium octaethyl porphyrin (PdOEP) as a sensitizer (0.03-0.7 wt%). The upconversion intensity was studied as a function of DPA and PdOEP contents and the results suggest that upconversion is optimal for DPA and PdOEP weight fractions of 34 and 0.05 wt% respectively.

Several optical upconverting schemes are known to cause an anti-Stokes shift, *i.e.*, the emanating photons have a higher energy than the incident electromagnetic radiation (Fig. 1).¹⁻³ While most upconverting processes require coherent, high-power light produced by lasers (*e.g.* second- or third-harmonic generation, two-photon absorption emission), upconversion by triplet-triplet annihilation (TTA-UC) is feasible at much lower power densities and with non-coherent, polychromatic excitation.^{4,5} The framework is therefore attractive for a range of applications, for example biological imaging and display techniques.⁶⁻¹² Perhaps the biggest promise of TTA-UC is that it can overcome the Shockley-Queisser solar power conversion limit,¹³⁻¹⁵ as it permits harnessing photons from the portion of the solar spectrum beyond a solar cell's bandgap.^{16,17}

The TTA-UC process relies on a series of energy transfer steps between a pair of chromophores, a sensitizer and an emitter (Fig. 1).^{3,18-22} The sensitizer absorbs incident photons and undergoes intersystem crossing, before a triplet excited state is transferred to the emitter. Two excited emitter molecules then form an encounter complex, and via a triplet-triplet annihilation step an emitter singlet excited state is populated. Delayed fluorescence from that singlet manifold ultimately leads to emission of an upconverted photon.

Since its discovery in the 1960s, TTA-UC has long been limited to liquid solutions, in which the intermolecular energy transfer steps are facilitated by high degrees of translational and rotational mobility.^{5,23} Since solvent-based TTA-UC systems exhibit several drawbacks for practical applications, including limited lifetime¹ and complex implementation,^{6,8,24-27} the discovery that TTA-UC could be achieved in properly chosen polymers²⁸ has triggered new interest solid upconverting

materials.⁷ The first examples of TTA-UC in polymers were based on physical mixtures of sensitizers in conjugated polymers.^{3,29} One further improvement towards more applicable polymeric upconverting systems was the fabrication of blends of suitable chromophores with a rubbery polymer matrix.²⁸ To avoid aggregation, the concentration of the chromophores was kept below 0.001 wt% and 0.02 wt% for the sensitizer and the emitter respectively. TTA-UC was only observed in the rubbery regime above the glass transition temperature (T_g), which is consistent with the requirement of translational and rotational mobility to enable the necessary bimolecular energy transfer processes.³⁰ The concept has been extended to several chromophore pairs and rubbery matrices,^{27,28,31} and was also used to fabricate upconverting nanoparticles and -fibers.^{6,7,32-34}

Based on the hypothesis that Dexter-type energy transfer should allow for TTA-UC in glassy materials, several groups started to pursue the investigation of materials with high chromophore content.^{2,31,35-38} While high-chromophore-content blends usually suffer from phase-separation effects,^{39,40} we demonstrated that this problem can be overcome by quenching, and therefore kinetically trapping, melt-processed homogeneous mixtures of palladium octaethylporphyrin (PdOEP) and 9,10-diphenylanthracene (DPA), a commonly used sensitizer/emitter pair, and poly(methyl methacrylate).⁴¹ At a maximum DPA content of 20 wt. %, these blends convert green into blue light at power densities as low as 34 mW/cm². Oligomers featuring covalently attached Ruthenium tris-bipyridine as sensitizer and DPA as emitter¹⁵ represent an alternative strategy for high-chromophore content materials, although upconversion in this system was limited by incomplete energy transfer.

Here, we report new upconverting copolymers with covalently tethered DPA emitter moieties (Fig. 2(a)). The design is based on the hypothesis that maximizing the emitter content would lead to a high TTA-UC efficiency on account of effective intermolecular energy transfer;⁴² de-mixing phenomena prevent the creation of such compositions by simple blending. Since only small amounts of the sensitizer are required, we opted to blend the DPA copolymers with PdOEP, which allowed us to readily vary the composition and explore its influence on the upconverting properties.

Thus, the new DPA-containing methacrylate monomer DPAMA was synthesized in two steps from the previously reported 9-bromo-10-phenylanthracene (Fig. 2 and Scheme S1†).⁴³ A palladium-catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura coupling between 9-bromo-10-phenylanthracene and 4-(3-hydroxypropyl) benzeneboronic acid afforded DPA(CH₂)₃OH,⁴⁴ which was reacted with methacryloyl chloride to prepare the corresponding methacrylic ester. The propyl spacer between the emitter and the polymerizable handle was selected to mitigate π - π stacking of the DPA motifs, and to maintain some flexibility while promoting efficient energy transfer between emitters in the glass. Furthermore, the spacer limits steric

hindrance around the vinyl group, which may hamper polymerization and ultimately preclude the formation of high molecular weight chains. A homopolymer of DPAMA (Table 1, Polymer 1) was synthesized by free radical polymerization. This material contains the maximally achievable chromophore content of 72 wt% (calculated on the basis of the neat DPA motif). Copolymers with a lower DPA content (poly(DPAMA-co-MMA)) were synthesized by copolymerization of DPAMA with methyl methacrylate (MMA) to investigate the effect of the emitter concentration. Polymers with 54, 34, 26, 17, and 8 wt% of DPA were thus prepared by free radical copolymerization with MMA (Table 1, Polymers 2-6). To avoid typical complications associated with high degrees of conversion, the polymerization reactions were terminated at yields of 35 - 69 %. The copolymer compositions determined by ^1H NMR spectroscopy correlate well with the monomer feed ratios (Table 1, Fig. S5-S10 \dagger), although it appears that the incorporation of MMA is slightly preferred. The number-average molecular weight M_n of the copolymers ranges from 89,000 to 260,000 g/mol with a molar-mass dispersity (\bar{D}) of 1.9 - 2.5, as expected for the free radical polymerization conditions applied (Fig. S11-S16 \dagger). For the DPAMA homopolymer 1 a somewhat higher \bar{D} (3.8) and lower M_n (62,000) were observed, suggesting a somewhat sluggish homopolymerization. In view of the sterically demanding side chain this finding is not surprising and we note that the effects had no appreciable influence (*vide infra*) on the relevant physical properties of the homopolymer 1.⁴⁵

The thermal properties of the new polymers were studied by thermogravimetric analyses (TGA, Fig. S17 \dagger) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Fig. S18-S24 \dagger). TGA puts the onset of the thermal decomposition above 300 °C. Besides the characteristic glass transitions, the DSC traces show no other signals and confirm that all polymers are amorphous. T_g increases with increasing DPAMA content from 123 °C (neat PMMA) to 150 °C (DPAMA homopolymer 1). Especially at low DPAMA content the observed T_g increase was higher than predicted by the Fox equation for statistical copolymers (Fig. S24 \dagger , Equation S1 \dagger).

To assess the optical absorption and photoluminescence properties of the new polymers, thin films were prepared by spin-coating onto glass substrates and analyzed by UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopy (Fig. S25-S26 \dagger). The absorption spectra show the characteristic vibrational fingerprint of DPA, with maxima at 340, 360, 380 and 405 nm; they match the absorption spectrum of neat DPA in chloroform and the thickness-normalized absorbance increases linearly with the DPA content (Fig. S26 \dagger). The covalent tethering of the DPA motif to a methacrylate backbone permits to create high-chromophore content polymers with spectroscopic features that mirror those of dilute solutions, although we note that concentration quenching may be at play in the case of polymers with high DPA content (*vide infra*).

To impart the new polymers with upconverting properties, they were blended with PdOEP, which is a well-known sensitizer for the unmodified DPA motif. Optically transparent films comprising polymers 1-6 and between 0.002 and 0.33 wt% PdOEP were prepared by either solution-casting (Method A) or compression-molding (Method B, Scheme 2(b)). A processing temperature of 160 °C was selected for the compression-molding step, which is above the T_g of all (co)polymers. Both processing methods enabled the preparation of homogeneous, highly transparent films (Table S1 \dagger , Fig. S27 \dagger). Interestingly, films containing the same emitter content as copolymer 3 but prepared by simple blending of DPA into a PMMA matrix displayed the characteristic haziness associated with crystallization of DPA (Fig. S27 \dagger). This observation was

further corroborated by DSC (Fig. S28 \dagger), where crystallization and melting peaks were both observed at 170 and 210 °C, respectively. Interestingly, the DSC of the blends of copolymer 3 displayed a notable decrease in T_g during the first heating (100 °C instead of 134 °C) for neat samples. This decrease could be attributed due to the formation of DPA-rich domains overtime or simply to the processing conditions. The second heating curves showed a recovery of the original T_g value (133 °C, Fig. S28 \dagger). The morphology of polymer blends of copolymers 3 and 6 and PdOEP (0.05 wt%) prepared by Method B was further characterized by small-angle X-Ray scattering (SAXS) and optical microscopy (Fig. S29-S30 \dagger). No features indicating microphase segregation or crystallization of DPA were detected by X-ray scattering (Fig. S29 \dagger). However, a faint signal at $q = 1.3 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ could be observed in the case of copolymer 3, which might simply arise due to packing considerations of a relatively high volume fraction of DPA. Furthermore, when observed under cross-polarizer (Fig. S30 \dagger), none of the samples showed any birefringence, which further corroborates the absence of large-scale DPA crystallization.

An initial evaluation of the TTA-UC effect was conducted with materials containing 0.05 wt% of PdOEP; this concentration was chosen based on the previously reported results for PMMA/DPA/PdOEP blends,⁴¹ where the TTA-UC relative intensity decreased with higher porphyrin contents, presumably on account of sensitizer aggregation.^{41,46} The corresponding emission spectra of UC films, acquired upon excitation at 370 nm, also resemble the DPA fluorescence in solution, although the inverse relation between emission intensity and DPA content appears to indicate considerable concentration quenching (Fig. S31 \dagger).

Upon irradiation with the light of a 2 mW green He-Ne laser operating at 543 nm, all films made from the blends based on copolymers 2-5 (processed by Methods A or B) exhibited notable blue emission that was clearly detectable by the unaided eye (Fig. 3). Spectrophotometric analysis (Fig. S32 \dagger) reveals emission spectra that are characteristic of upconverted emission from DPA. Upconverted emission was neither observed for the PdOEP-doped homopolymer 1, likely due to concentration quenching caused by the large content of DPA, nor for copolymer 6, which contains only a small amount of the emitter and therefore does not support energy transfer away from the sensitizer. This is clearly evident by the pronounced PdOEP phosphorescence in the latter material (Fig. S32 \dagger). To develop a better understanding of how the composition influences the TTA-UC process, the upconversion intensity and the intensity of residual PdOEP phosphorescence between 620-680 nm were measured as a function of emitter content for films made by Methods A and B (Fig. 4(a,b)). For this series of experiments, the PdOEP content was fixed at 0.05 wt%. A survey of the data, which were normalized for the film thickness to compare relative intensities, shows that both the DPA content and the processing conditions exert a significant influence on the upconversion intensity. Solution-cast films exhibited substantially lower upconversion intensity than their compression-molded counterparts (Fig. 4(a)). The difference points to some aggregation of PdOEP in the solution-processed samples, whereas rapid cooling from the melt may promote kinetic trapping of molecularly dissolved blends in the melt-processed materials. In both series, the relative upconversion intensity increased with the DPA content to reach a maximum for copolymer 3 (Fig. 4(a)), which contains 34 wt% DPA. The residual phosphorescence (Fig. 4(b)) decreases in a reverse manner, and is virtually completely quenched at a DPA content of 26 wt% or more, indicating efficient Dexter-type energy transfer of triplet excited states between PdOEP and DPA. Interestingly, Fig. 4a reveals that the TTA-UC relative intensity

is decreased if the DPA content is decreased beyond 34 wt%. As indicated by fluorescence measurements of the neat polymers (*vide supra*, Fig. S31†) this effect appears to be related to concentration quenching of the DPA fluorescence. Interestingly, despite the anticipated absence of well-defined phase separation or crystallization in the upconverting films thanks to the DPA tethering (Fig. S27-S30†), the very high DPA concentrations probably allowed for the formation of DPA-rich domains, within which triplet exciton hopping and annihilation could occur efficiently.

The power dependence of the upconverted fluorescence was examined as a function of incident excitation intensity for the composition exhibiting the highest upconversion intensity (copolymer **3**, Method B, Fig. 4(c)). The excitation power density was varied between 32 and 320 mW/cm² by using a set of neutral density filters. The upconverted emission intensity was plotted as function of excitation power density in a double logarithmic plot (Fig. 4(d)). The graph shows that in the compression-molded films the relation is pseudo-linear, with an exponent of 1.46. The corresponding experiment revealed a slope of 1.70 for the solution-cast material (Fig. S30†), supporting improved TTA relative intensity in melt-processed vs. solution-cast films.² Operational stability is a key feature for future applications and devices and the PMMA-matrix offers protection from oxygen quenching and photodegradation. In order to probe photostability, upconversion was monitored in 4 month-old samples under constant excitation at 320 mW/cm² for the most efficient sample (copolymer **3**, Method B), which displayed an exceptional stability by retaining more than 80% of its initial UC-intensity after 3.5h of continuous laser irradiation (Fig. S35†).

Copolymer **3**, which displayed the highest upconversion intensity when doped with 0.05 wt% PdOEP, was chosen to probe the influence of the PdOEP content; additional concentrations of 0.002 and 0.33 wt% were explored. A comparison of the (not normalized) upconverted emission spectra of compression-molded films (Fig. 5d) shows that the highest upconverted emission intensity was observed for a film of the blend with 0.05 wt% PdOEP, even though the absorbance of the film comprising 0.33 wt% is much higher (Fig. 5b). A similar effect was previously reported for PMMA/DPA/PdOEP blends,⁴¹ where the TTA-UC efficiency decreased with higher porphyrin contents, presumably on account of sensitizer aggregation. Interestingly, however, we now observe that at least if incorporated at a concentration of 0.33 wt% the PdOEP appears to quench the fluorescence of DPA when the latter is directly excited at 370 nm (Fig. 5(a) and (c)). Strong decrease of DPA-fluorescence of the same sample was also observed when irradiating at 340 nm, where only DPA absorbs efficiently, or at 395 nm, where both DPA and PdOEP absorb strongly (Fig. S36†). Therefore, the reduced fluorescence intensity does not seem to stem from increased direct radiation absorption by PdOEP. These results are consistent with the formation of exciplexes or other non-radiative relaxation pathways induced by the presence of the sensitizer, *e.g.* energy transfer from the emitter to the sensitizer. Interestingly, the ratio of sensitizer to emitter is approximately sevenfold smaller than for most efficient solutions of the same pair. This finding can be explained by the lack of mobility of the emitter in the solid state and the necessity to ensure higher concentrations of DPA to harvest the triplet excited states of the porphyrin sensitizer.

In summary, we utilized covalent tethering of DPA emitters to a polymeric backbone to vary the emitter content in glassy upconverting materials without phase separation effects. This methodology allowed us to prepare upconverting materials that cover a wide range of emitter contents and fabricate self-

standing glassy upconverting samples that upconvert the incident light of a 543 nm 2 mW laser into deep-blue light that can readily be detected by the unaided eye. The data allowed us to establish a preliminary efficiency diagram for the compression-molded polymers (Table S2† and Fig. S34†), which shows that optimal concentrations exist for *both* chromophores: 34 wt% for the emitter and 0.05 wt% for the sensitizer.

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Notes and references

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Fig. 1 (a) Schematic representation of the various steps involved in upconversion by triplet-triplet annihilation. Low-energy light is absorbed to populate the singlet excited state of a sensitizer ($1S^*$), which undergoes rapid intersystem crossing (ISC) to its triplet excited state ($3S^*$). The triplet excited state of an emitter ($3E^*$) is then populated by triplet-triplet energy transfer (TTET) from the sensitizer, before triplet-triplet annihilation (TTA) between two $3E^*$ results in the population of the singlet excited state of one emitter ($1E^*$) and delayed fluorescence is finally observed from that singlet level ($1E^* \rightarrow GS$ transition). Solid lines represent the intended radiative processes (excitation and emission). Dotted lines represent undesired non-radiative and radiative decay pathways. (b) Illustration of the anti-Stokes shift and energy gain.

Fig 2 (a) Chemical structures of the sensitizer palladium octaethylporphyrin (PdOEP), emitter diphenylanthracene (DPA)-containing methacrylate monomer (DPAMA), and poly(DPAMA-co-MMA), the copolymer series **1-6** with covalently attached DPA emitters. (b) Schematic representation of the fabrication of glassy upconverting films by compression-molding. Poly(DPAMA-co-MMA) and PdOEP were premixed in toluene followed by drop-casting and evaporation of the solvent at 105 °C. The final films were as produced by compression-molding at 160 °C applying light pressure (Method B).

Fig. 3 Picture of the TTA-UC process in a film based on a blend of copolymer **3** and 0.05 wt% of PdOEP. The sample was prepared with Method B and is shown under excitation with a 2 mW HeNe laser at 543 nm (320 mW/cm²). The blue fluorescence in the center of the sample originates from TTA-UC. The green rays (incident and reflected beams) were made visible by using the fog created by liquid nitrogen as a scattering medium.

Fig. 4 Variation of (a) upconversion and (b) phosphorescence intensities normalized to film thickness as a function of DPA weight percent upon excitation at 543 nm (320 mW/cm²) of (co)polymer films containing 0.05 wt% of PdOEP. The films were prepared by solution-casting (Method A, circles) and melt-processing (Method B, squares). (c) Upconverted emission spectra of compression-molded films (Method B) of copolymer 3 with 0.05 % of PdOEP upon excitation with a HeNe laser at 543 nm at different excitation power densities as indicated in the graph. (d) Double logarithmic plot of the data shown in (c), and a least square fit of the data (slope = 1.46 for Method B).

Fig. 5 (a) Pictures of compression-molded films based on blends of polymer 3 and (from left) 0.33, 0.05, or 0.002 wt% PdOEP acquired under ambient illumination (top) or illumination with a 365 nm UV lamp. (b) Absorption spectra of compression-molded films based on blends of polymer 3 and 0.33, 0.05, or 0.002 wt% PdOEP. (c) Emission spectra of the same samples upon excitation at 370 nm. (d) Upconversion emission intensity of compression-molded films of the same samples upon excitation with a 2mW HeNe laser at 543 nm.

Table 1 Characterization of the different (co)polymers prepared by free radical polymerization of DPAMA and MMA.

Polymer	Composition			Molecular weight		Yield %
	DPAMA/MMA Feed (mol/mol)	DPAMA/MMA in copolymer(mol/mol) ^{a)}	DPA content (wt%) ^{a)}	$M_n^{b)}$ (g/mol)	$D^{b)}$	
1	1/0	1/0	72	62 000	3.8	69
2	1/3	1/2	54	89 000	2.0	50
3	1/5	1/4	34	110 000	1.9	66
4	1/15	1/7	26	160 000	2.1	35
5	1/20	1/16	17	240 000	2.0	41
6	1/45	1/40	8	260 000	2.5	54

^{a)}The ratio of DPAMA/MMA in the copolymers was determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy by comparing the integrations of the benzylic protons of DPAMA at $\delta = 4.0$ ppm with the ester protons of both DPAMA and MMA at $\delta = 3.5$ ppm. The DPA weight content in polymer was calculated from the DPAMA/MMA ratio (Fig. S5†-S10†). ^{b)}The number-average molecular weights (M_n) and the molar mass dispersity (D) of the (co)polymers were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) in THF vs. PMMA standard (Fig. S11†-S16†).

ToC Figure

